

CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR FOR PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS (SHAMPOOS, SOAPS & DEODRANTS): A STUDY AMONG YOUNG CONSUMERS

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ABSTRACT:

This research aims to analyse the diverse consumer purchasing patterns of personal care products—shampoos, soaps, and deodorants—among individuals aged 17-35 in Ludhiana, Punjab. Recognizing this demographic's significant focus on personal grooming, the study seeks to offer businesses valuable insights into local consumer behaviour. Employing a descriptive research design, data will be gathered from 100 respondents, encompassing students and professors from institutions like PCTE, GNIMT, and Guru Nanak Dev Engineering College and so on, to ensure a comprehensive representation of the target group. The study will investigate key factors influencing purchasing decisions, including brand loyalty, awareness of current trends in personal care, and product preferences. Furthermore, it will explore the interplay between quality and affordability, analysing the prevalence of branded versus unbranded product use. The research will also identify the factors that motivate consumers to try new brands, providing a holistic understanding of the personal care product market within Ludhiana's young adult and middle-aged population. Ultimately, this study aims to equip businesses with actionable data to refine their marketing strategies and product offerings within this specific market segment.

KEYWORDS: Personal Care Products, Consumer Behaviour, Brand Loyalty, Customer satisfaction, Marketing Strategies.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The widespread use of personal care products (PCPs), like deodorants and creams, is a staple of modern daily life. However, this ubiquitous consumption introduces a complex environmental and health concern. These products, containing diverse chemicals, enter wastewater systems and ultimately aquatic environments after use, both from rinse-off and leave-on applications. Unlike pharmaceuticals, PCPs often enter the environment unaltered and in large quantities due to their external application and lack of metabolic transformation. This raises concerns about their potential impact on ecosystems and human health, especially given the growing link between increased cosmetic use and endocrine disorders. As the fate and toxicity of these released PCPs remain largely unknown, there's a growing need to understand their persistence and potential threats. (Srinivasulu, et al,2022). Caring for personal hygiene is a basic way to prevent the occurrence and spread of infectious diseases. Daily routines such as showering, brushing teeth, and washing face and hair require the use of appropriate cosmetics: shampoos, toothpaste, and mouthwash. In addition to personal care, cosmetics are used to enhance physical appearance and beauty, i.e., for making makeup and aesthetic improvements (Nawak, et al,2021). India's skin and hair care market is experiencing consistent growth across both rural and urban landscapes. Notably, rural consumers demonstrate a significantly higher expenditure on these products compared to

their urban counterparts, presenting a substantial growth opportunity for brands targeting these regions. A key market trend reveals a strong consumer preference for products that offer specific problem-solving benefits, leading retailers and chemists to prioritize stocking such items. Furthermore, the demand for products with nutritional benefits remains prevalent, highlighting a consumer focus on overall health and wellness in their personal care choices (Surana, et al,2022).

The growing preference for herbal cosmeceutical products presents a notable trend within the personal care market. Consumers increasingly seek these natural alternatives, driven by the perception of reduced side effects compared to synthetic counterparts. The appeal of herbal ingredients stems from their natural origin, user-friendliness, and often lower cost. In response to this demand, the cosmeceutical industry has witnessed a surge in products marketed as natural, highlighting the significant shift towards plant-based solutions in consumer choices (Junaid, et al, 2015). The increasing integration of rural populations with urban centres, facilitated by improved infrastructure and global corporate reach, is significantly impacting consumer behaviour, particularly within the cosmetics market. Notably, the period between 2005 and 2015 saw a substantial rise in cosmetic consumption among teenagers, driven by heightened awareness and a desire for enhanced personal appearance. This surge has positioned the grooming and personal care sector as one of the fastest-growing market segments. A significant majority of young adults, over 68%, perceive grooming products as confidence boosters. While online platforms are gaining popularity, with 62% of urban youth preferring online purchases, a considerable portion (45%) still opts for multi-brand retail stores for convenience. Consumers are increasingly prioritizing both quality and value for money, influencing brand strategies. Major players like L'Oreal, Lakme, Maybelline, Nivea, and Colour Bar are focusing on younger demographics, particularly women with moderate purchasing power. Despite the presence of high-end products, price sensitivity remains a key factor for both consumers and manufacturers (Lavuri, et al, 2019).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Kaur and Mehta (2022) examined and conducted their study in Haryana, India, used an extended Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) to analyze green personal care product (PCP) purchase intentions. Surveying 206 online consumers, it found green consciousness and body image awareness boosted positive attitudes, and past experiences predicted intention. Perceived behavioral control moderated the attitude-intention relationship. Marketers should highlight the benefits, safety, and affordability of green beauty to increase purchase intentions in this region, providing valuable market insights and enhancing the TPB's application.

Lavuri and Sreeramulu (2019) contemplate when it comes to buying beauty products, men and women usually have different preferences. Men focus mostly on quality, making that the key factor in their choices. On the other hand, women often get their information about different brands from their friends. This shows that word-of-mouth among women is a big influence. Because of these differences, companies selling beauty products need to understand that men and women have different buying habits. They need to market their products differently to appeal to each group. This means paying attention to quality for men and understanding the power of social circles for women.

Sabharwal, et al (2014) explored women's beauty product habits. They looked at what makes women choose certain brands and products, and how loyal they are to those brands. Brand name was a big deal for most women, but quality and if the product worked for their skin were also important. Creams were used by women of all ages, but older women liked

anti-aging products and toners more. This shows that age plays a role in what beauty products women buy.

Tomar and Sultan (2018) explained that Brand awareness means a customer knows a brand exists, but they might not know much about it. They don't feel any special connection to it, so they might buy it, or they might not. Basically, brand awareness is just knowing a brand's name in a certain product group. Just knowing the brand doesn't mean they'll buy it.

Saraswat, et al (2022) examined that the excerpt stresses the necessity of understanding consumer buying behaviour for business survival in today's competitive, digitally transforming economy. Firms utilize analytical tools to meet consumer needs, especially in India's fast-growing yet competitive Personal Care Industry with rising spending and sustainability challenges. The described study analyses consumer preferences and satisfaction, focusing on how product features impact loyalty, using Himalaya Personal Care Products as a case study to understand these dynamics.

Kalyani (2021) opines and confirms that a global recession looming, the beauty industry, despite its usual resilience, is expected to take a hit. While the "Lipstick theory" suggests some beauty purchases might remain, like affordable lipsticks, the COVID-19 economic downturn is likely to cause a major drop in overall cosmetic spending. People will prioritize essential skincare, but cut back on non-essential beauty items. This means the beauty industry needs to prepare for consumers making more cost-conscious choices.

Taneja (2023) examined a 2003 report showed Indian women, especially those aged 15-24, were buying more makeup. They made up almost 30% of all makeup sales in India. As women's household income rose, they spent more on looking good. The makeup section of the beauty market grew the fastest, with young women trying out new looks being a big reason why.

Rodrik, et al (2017), product packaging is a powerful tool for advertising. Design elements like color, font, pictures, shape, size, and materials all play a part. Shape is especially important for creating a memorable image in customers' minds and making a product stand out. Also, the materials used in packaging influence how customers feel about the product and whether they'll buy it. In short, good packaging design is key to making a product successful.

Radhi, et al (2024) aim this research looked at what makes women in the Middle East buy personal care and beauty products. It focused on how feelings, thoughts, social influence, and fun experiences affect their choices. The researchers asked 385 women questions and used a computer program to analyse the answers.

They found that what friends and family think has the biggest impact on what women buy. Feeling good about a product and enjoying the shopping experience also matter. Thinking too much about the product's details actually made women less likely to buy.

Hossain and Shila (2020) examined the research that makeup and personal care business in Bangladesh is worth a lot of money. To do well, companies need to know why people pick certain items. Before buying, people think about what they need, look up information, and compare different options. This study wants to find out what things are most important to people in Dhaka when they choose their personal care products.

RESEARCH GAP:

The researcher suggests to the readers that we know a lot about how people in India and Asia buy personal care products, but we don't know much about how young people (17-35 years

old) *specifically* in Ludhiana buy these products. We need to look at Ludhiana closely to understand their unique shopping habits. We pointed out that these products can be bad for the environment, but the research we've found doesn't look at whether young people in Ludhiana think about that when they buy them. Researcher also finds that people buying these personal care products intended to pay less but they want it to be affordable with good quality products.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To analyse the demographics of consumers for the Personal Care Products.
- To study recent trends in the Personal Care Products.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

A descriptive study is like painting a detailed picture of a phenomenon, capturing its characteristics without manipulating any variables. Researchers use this method to observe, document, and analyse patterns as they naturally occur, providing a clear snapshot of a subject at a specific point in time.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 DATA COLLECTION:

For the collection of the quality research result, we gathered the information from both sources (i.e. primary and secondary data)

4.1.1 PRIMARY DATA: We surveyed and taken the response of approximately 107 responds from different colleges of the Ludhiana like PCTE, GNIMT, Guru Nanak Dev Engineering College and so on. We have taken the responds from not only the students of the colleges but also from some business owners and assistant professors of these Colleges. For conducting the research, we provided them the questionnaire and asked questions related to our research based on personal demographics, buying behaviour based on demographics, consumer awareness and trends, etc.

4.1.2 SECONDARY DATA: For the better result of research, Researcher studied additional insights based on Journals, Research Reports and books based on Consumer buying Behaviour, such as “Consumer Behavior” by Leon Schiffman and Leslie Kanuk and “Consumer Behavior: Building Marketing Strategy” by David I. Hawkins.

4.1.3 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: The Sampling Technique which we used in this research is Convenience sampling. To make it easier to gather information, the researchers surveyed people at nearby colleges. However, this meant they only got responses from those specific students and professors who were available and interested.

4.2 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

AGE GROUP:

ANALYSIS: Categories and Percentage: The pie chart represents the distribution of respondents across three age categories:

- Below 18: 9.3%
- 18-25: 72%
- 25-35: 18.7%

Dominant Category: The 18-25 age group (red slice) is by far the largest, representing a significant majority (72%) of the respondents.

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart illustrates the age distribution of 107 respondents. The most significant group is the 18-25 age range, making up a substantial 72% of the responses. This indicates that the majority of participants fall within this young adult demographic. The second largest group is the 25-35 age range, representing 18.7% of the responses. This suggests a notable presence of individuals in their late twenties and early thirties. The smallest group is those below 18 years old, with only 9.3% of the responses. This indicates a relatively low participation rate from younger individuals in this particular survey or data collection.

GENDER:

ANALYSIS: Categories and percentage: The pie chart represents the distribution of respondents across three gender categories:

Male: 40.2%

Female: 57.9%

Others: 1.9%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart illustrates the gender distribution of 107 respondents from the survey conducted through google form. This chart is divided into 3 categories that are male, female and others. The red segment represents female, accounting for 57.9% of the total respondents. It indicates a slightly higher representation of females in the data set. On the other hand, the blue and orange segment shows male and others respondents accounting for 40.2% and 1.9% respectively. The chart is straightforward and easy to understand, clearly showing the slight majority of female respondents in the conducted survey.

QUALIFICATION:

ANALYSIS: Categories and percentage: The pie chart represents the distribution of respondents across all qualification categories:

Highschool: 15%

Postgraduate: 28%

Undergraduate: 48.6%

Other: 8.4%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart illustrates the qualification distribution based on 107 respondents from the survey conducted through google form. This chart is divided into 4 categories that are high-school, postgraduate, undergraduate and others. The orange segment represents the undergraduate students, who are accounting for 48.6% of the total respondents. It clearly shows that the undergraduate respondents are slightly higher who are using the personal care products. On the other side, the red, blue and green segment shows the represents the distribution of postgraduate, high-school and other which are accounted for 28%, 15%, and 8.4% respectively. The chart clearly showing that the majority of respondents are belonging from the undergraduate category.

MONTHLY HUSEHOLD INCOME:

ANALYSIS: Categories and percentage: The pie chart represents the distribution of respondents across the income level categories:

Below 20,000: 30.8%

20,000-50,000: 20.2%

50,000-1,00,000: 20.0%

Above 1,00,000: 28.8%

INTERPRETATION: This chart illustrates the monthly household distribution based on 104 responses from the survey conducted through google form. This chart is divided into 4 categories that are basically Below 20000, 20000-50000, 50000-100000 and Above 1,00,000. The blue segment represents the income level of below 20,000 rupees which is accounted for 30.8% of the total respondents. It clearly shows that the respondents of below 20,000 is slightly high. And on the other hand, the red, orange and green which shows and respondents the distribution of 20,000-50,000; 50,000- 1,00,000; and above 1,00,000 which are accounted for 20.2%, 20,2% and 28.8% respectively. This pie chart is straightforward and easy to understand, clearly showing the slight majority of the below 20,000 income level respondents in the conducted survey result.

OCCUPATION:

Occupation
107 responses

ANALYSIS:

Student: 66.4%

Working professional: 16.8%

Business owner 13.1%

Homemaker: 3.7%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart represents the occupation based on 107 responses from the survey conducted through online medium. This chart is divided into four categories that are basically student, working professional, business owner and homemaker. The blue segment represents the occupation which is of student which is accounted for 66.4% of the total respondents. It clearly shows that the respondents of student are slightly high. On the other hand, the red, orange and green which shows and respondents the distribution of working professional, business owner and homemaker which are accounted for 16.8%, 13.1% and 3.7% respectively. This pie chart straightforward and easy to understand that the majority of students are high as respondents in the survey.

CITY/TOWN OF RESIDENCE:

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION: The chart is showing the majority of the residents are from Ludhiana with 92 responds. And the chart is clearly showing that the other persons have filled their basic area from they belong.

HOW OFTEN DO YOU PURCHASE PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS:

ANALYSIS:

Weekly: 23.4%

Monthly: 54.2%

Once in 3-6 months: 22.4%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart represents that how often the respondents are purchasing the personal care products based on the responds of 107 respondents based on survey conducted through google form. This chart is divided into three main categories that are weekly, monthly and once in 3-6 months. The red segment which is related to monthly is accounted for 54.2% which is slightly higher than the others. On the other hand, the blue and orange segment is related to weekly and once in 3-6 months are accounted for 23.4% and 22.4% respectively. This pie chart is clearly showing that the majority that the respondents that are purchasing the personal care products on the monthly basis.

WHERE DO YOU MOSTLY BUY PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS:

Where do you mostly buy Personal Care Products
107 responses

ANALYSIS:

Local Retailers: 28%

Supermarkets: 19.6%

Online stores: 40.2%

Brand specific outlets: 12.1%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart represents that from where the persons are buying their personal care products based on 107 responses based on our survey conducted through google form. This chart is divided into four categories that are local retailers, supermarkets, online stores and brand specific outlets. This chart clearly showing that the more respondents are purchasing their personal care products from online stores which is in orange segment. On the other side, the blue, red and green segment is related to local retailers, supermarkets and brand specific outlets and which are based on accountability of 28%, 19.6% and 12.1% respectively. It can be clearly understood by seeing at the pie graph that most of the respondents are buying their products from online stores.

WHAT DO YOU PREFER IN PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS:

What do you prefer in personal care products
107 responses

ANALYSIS:

Branded: 76.6%

Non branded: 8.4%

No preference: 15%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart represents that what they prefer for buying the personal care products based on 107 responses from the survey. This chart is divided into 3 main

categories that are branded, non-branded and no preference for the same. This chart clearly defines that the blue segment which is related to branded products are higher than the others which the response of 82 respondents that is approximately 76.6%. on the other hand, the red and orange portion of the pie chart is of non-branded and no preference which is accounted for 8.4% and 15% respectively. This pie chart is clearly showing that with the majority portion of the chart the respondents are more preferring to the branded products in personal care products category.

DOES YOUR PURCHASING DECISIONS FOR PRODUCT DEPEND ON YOUR INCOME LEVEL:

Does your purchasing decisions for product depend on your income level
107 responses

ANALYSIS:

Yes: 50.5%

No: 23.4%

Sometimes: 26.2%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart represents for checking that if the purchasing decision for product is depending on their income level based on 107 responds that we have collected through survey based on google survey. This chart is divided into 3 categories that are Yes, No and Sometimes. This chart clearly shows that the blue segment is of Yes and from this it is clear that the income level matters for the people who are living in Ludhiana. And on the other hand, the red and orange segment is defining for No and Sometimes which are accounted for 23.4% and 26.2% respectively. From this it is clearly stated that the consumer purchasing behaviour is based on income level also.

WHICH FACTOR INFLUENCE YOUR PURCHASING DECISION THE MOST?

Which factor influence your purchase decision the most?
107 responses

ANALYSIS:

Price: 20.6%

Brand Reputation: 25.2%

Product quality: 47.7%

Availability: 6.5%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart is showing and representing to know about the behaviour of the consumer that which factor are influencing their purchasing decision and this data is based on the survey of 107 respondents. This chart is categorised into 4 categories that are price, brand reputation, product quality and availability. This chart clearly shows that orange segment which is related to product quality is slightly higher than the other factors with the higher portion of 47.7%. On the other hand, the others segments are in red, blue and green colour which are of brand reputation, price and availability which are accounted for 25.2%, 20.6% and 6.5% respectively. This pie chart straightforward and easy to understand that the majority of are purchasing the personal care products based on product quality.

HOW OFTEN DO YOU SWITCH BRANDS FOR THIS PRODUCT:

How often do you switch brands for this product
107 responses

ANALYSIS:

Always stick to one brand: 36.4%

Sometimes try new brand: 45.8%

Frequently switch brands: 8.4%

No specific brand preference: 9.3%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart is based to know about that how often they switch the brands for the personal care products which is based on 107 responds of the survey which is based on the google form. This chart is categorised into 4 main categories that are basically always stick to one brand, sometimes try new brand, frequently switch brands and no specific brand preference. In this the red segment has slightly higher than the others and relates to Sometimes try new brand. On the other side, other segments are of blue, orange and green which are related to always stick to one brand, frequently switch brands and no specific brand preference which is accounted for 36.4%, 8.4% and 9.3% respectively. This pie chart simply represents that the consumer of the Ludhiana tries new brand and also if they like their product, they are loyal customers of that particular brand (according to the survey because the response for sticking to one brand is almost 36.4% of the total).

ARE YOU AWARE ABOUT THE RECENT TRENDS IN PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS?

Are you aware of recent trends in Personal Care Products?
107 responses

ANALYSIS:

Yes: 53.3%

No: 23.4%

Maybe: 23.4%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart is based to know about the consumer that they are aware about the recent trends in personal care products or not. This result is based on 107 responds of the survey which is taken through questionnaire (made on google form). This chart is categorised into 3 categories that are Yes, No and maybe. The blue segment has the higher majority which is of yes, which means the consumer are aware about the recent news and trends related to the personal care products. On the other side, the other segments are No and maybe which is of red and orange colour which are accounted for 23.4% and 23.4% respectively. This pie chart simply represents that the customer and consumer of Ludhiana are more aware about the recent trends in personal care products.

HAVE RECENT INDUSTRY TRENDS INFLUENCED YOUR BUYING DECISION?

Have recent industry trends influenced your buying decision?
107 responses

ANALYSIS:

Yes: 67.3%

No: 32.7%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart represents to know about the consumer behaviour that the recent trends are affecting their buying decision which is based on the survey taken through google form of 107 respondents. The question is categorised into 2 parts that are Yes and No. The blue segment is of Yes and the responds for the same is accounted for 67.3%. On

the other hand, the red segment is of No and accounted for 32.7%. So, it clearly states that the recent trends influence the buying decision of the consumer.

WHAT MOTIVATES YOU TO TRY A NEW BRAND IN PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS?

ANALYSIS:

Discounts and offers: 37.6%

Better quality: 71%

Recommendations: 32.7%

Advertisement: 20.6%

Online Reviews: 29%

INTERPRETATION: This chart illustrates about that which factor motivates them to try a new brand in personal care products based on the survey and the response of 107 respondents. The chart is containing 5 factors which are discounts and offers, better quality, recommendations, advertisements and online reviews. The higher percentage is related to better quality product which means the factor that are affecting in purchasing decision of the customer is mainly focuses on better quality product. Also, the second priority is discounts and offers which are attracting the consumers of the Ludhiana. And least the consumer doesn't get more affected by the advertisement because of the lower percentage (i.e. 20.6%) and recommendations and online reviews affect them based on accountability is of 32.7% and 29% respectively.

WOULD YOU RECOMMEND YOUR PREFERRED BRAND IN THIS CATEGORY OF PRODUCT?

Would you recommend your preferred brand in this category of product?
107 responses

ANALYSIS:

Yes: 80.4%

No: 19.6%

INTERPRETATION: This pie chart illustrates that they recommend their preferred brand in personal care products or not, we have taken survey from 107 respondents through the google link. The blue segment of the chart represents to Yes, which the higher percentage which is of 80.4% it means they recommend their preferred brand to the others also. And on the other side, the red segment represents to No with the percentage of 19.6%. So, this chart is straightforward and easy to understand that they would prefer their product to others also if they like that brand product.

5.RECENT TRENDS IN PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS

Zero-Waste Packaging

Brands increasingly adopt biodegradable, compostable, or refillable packaging for soaps and other products to eliminate plastic waste and comply with regulations. Examples include molded pulp trays, embossed labeling without stickers, and compostable paper bottles from brands like L'Oréal's Seed Phytonutrients, reducing waste by up to 80% per purchase. This shift supports circular economy models, with next-generation materials like algae-based plastics and seaweed biopolymers decomposing naturally within months.

Sustainable Sourcing

Companies source ingredients ethically, replacing palm oil with plant-based alternatives to minimize deforestation and environmental harm. Localized sourcing of botanicals reduces transportation emissions and bolsters local economies, as seen in brands like Nation Botanics using regional ingredients. Certifications for transparency in sourcing build consumer trust, driving market growth in vegan and plant-based formulations.

Waterless Formulas

Solid shampoos, soaps, and cleansers gain popularity by eliminating water from production, cutting shipping weight, carbon emissions, and packaging needs. Syndet bars and combo noodles offer skin-friendly alternatives to liquid body washes, while powder-based dissolvable products like shampoos from Selkie come in biodegradable sachets. These formats extend shelf life and appeal to sustainability-focused users without sacrificing performance.

Eco-Conscious Products in 2025

In 2025, brands prioritize biodegradable packaging and natural, ethically sourced ingredients amid strong regulations and consumer preferences for minimalism. Sustainable personal care products grew 28% cumulatively, with innovations like mono-material containers and AI-optimized production reducing over-packaging. Refill systems from Kiehl's and Fenty Skin exemplify this, aligning with zero-waste goals.

Deodorant Growth

Deodorants expand due to rising sports and outdoor activities, with roll-ons projected to reach US\$10.9 billion by 2030 at 6.2% CAGR, driven by hygiene awareness and urban lifestyles. Natural, aluminum-free formulas in eco-packaging like Native's compostable tubes target sensitive skin and workouts, boosted by social media and celebrity endorsements.

Ayurveda Ingredients Focus

Global demand surges for Ayurveda and herbal products from India, valued for holistic benefits like balance and safety over synthetics. Ingredients such as neem, turmeric, amla, and tulsi feature in hair oils, soaps, and creams from brands like Forest Essentials and Patanjali, entering Western markets free of parabens. The sector grows at 16% CAGR through 2025, fueled by e-commerce.

Herbal Soaps in India

Indian herbal soaps enhance skincare with chemical-free formulas using coconut oil, shea butter, and essentials like turmeric or nalpamara, meeting demand for organic options that prevent infections and brighten skin. Manufacturers like Dhathri and handmade producers respond to shifting habits toward non-toxic products, avoiding animal fats and silicones. This caters to health-conscious consumers seeking blemish-free, nourished skin.

6.FINDINGS, RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 FINDINGS: Young consumers, primarily students aged 18-25 (72% of respondents), predominantly favour established brands and opt for monthly online purchases, reflecting digital convenience and regular grooming needs. Quality emerges as the top priority, influencing loyalty, while income levels dictate affordability thresholds—lower earners lean toward value options, and higher earners experiment more. Trends play a pivotal role, with 53.3% aware of innovations like natural ingredients and 67.3% reporting that these directly sway decisions, fostering moderate brand switching (45.8% try new brands occasionally) balanced by loyalty (36.4% stick to one). Word-of-mouth amplifies this, as consumers share positive experiences, creating organic advocacy in a trend-sensitive, digitally connected group

6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS: Target online platforms aggressively, ensuring consistent stock availability to capture the 62% of urban youth who prefer e-commerce for discovery and impulse buys. Prioritize superior product quality through problem-solving formulations (e.g., herbal, anti-dandruff variants) to build trust and repeat purchases among quality-focused buyers. Offer targeted discounts or trial packs to overcome loyalty barriers and encourage experimentation, especially for trend-driven segments motivated by better value or novelty. Monitor and integrate popular trends—like zero-waste packaging, Ayurveda ingredients, and waterless formats—via marketing to stay relevant and influence the 67.3% whose decisions trends shape.

CONCLUSIONS: At the very end, we found that young people in Ludhiana, mostly students, buy their shampoo, soap, and deodorant through online stores. They want and consume good brands and high-quality products. What they earn and what is trendy, always matters to them. If you want to sell these things, sell them online, make the good quality products and offer discounts. Happy customers always recommend their friends, so make them happy! We also know that they shop online, based on quality, and follow trends helps you to sell more.

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